

RRI2SCALE – Training Questionnaire (M2.1)

Title: Evaluation of the training on the implementation of stakeholder dialogues

Description: The current questionnaire aims to measure the impact of the RRI2SCALE training on implementing stakeholder dialogues that took place last autumn.

#	Identifier	Question	Very much	Some what	Neutral	Not really	Not at all	Undecided
1	SP.DS.2	Did your participation in the RRI2SCALE training help you to organise the multistakeholder dialogue (or the Scenario Exploration System - SES session, as commonly called) of your region?						
2	SP.EP.8	Did your participation in the RRI2SCALE training improve your skills to better design and implement strategic planning processes with public engagement?						
3	SP.EP.5	Did the RRI2SCALE training familiarise you with practices to encourage interactiveness among stakeholders when you organise strategic planning processes?						
4	SP.EP.1	Did the RRI2SCALE training familiarise you with practices to capture weak societal signals (e.g., people’s feelings) when you organise strategic planning processes?						
5	SP.DS.1	Do you believe that familiarising policy-makers with estimations about future developments (e.g., technological, demographical and research developments) in their region is crucial for their strategic planning process?						

Do you represent an organisation that is part of the RRI2SCALE consortium?

- Yes
- No
- Other

Thank you for your feedback!